

The Electrodeposition of Zinc and Nickel in the Presence of Acetylacetone : The Behaviour of the Ligand as Both an Inhibitor and a Depolarizer

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The electrodeposition of zinc and nickel from aqueous solutions is investigated in the presence of acetylacetone at pH values of 4.0 and 5.2 respectively. The current efficiency of the zinc and nickel deposition is dependent on the concentration of acetylacetone and the applied current density. The ligand behaves as a surface active substance as well as a depolarizer. The surface activity is more pronounced in the case of the nickel deposition whereas the ligand is reduced during the zinc deposition. The cathodic behaviour of metal ions is compatible with the suggestion that the ligand could manifest itself as both an inhibitor and a depolarizer. The throwing power of the metal deposition baths is markedly influenced by the addition of acetylacetone.

THE theory of complex formation was the first quantitative treatment that led to an understanding of the role of surface active substances (S.A.S.) in electrode processes¹. The adsorption of the S.A.S. on the electrode followed by its coordination with the metal ion was the reason behind the inhibition effects of the electrode process. It has been reported² that an increase in the S.A.S. concentration would be accompanied by a parallel increase in polarization up to a certain concentration above which polarization will attain a constant value.

Several types of organic compounds were used as S.A.S. which included quaternary ammonium salts, sodium salts of sulphonic acid derivatives, and long chain alcohols³. Various theories were suggested to explain the effect of the S.A.S. on the electrode processes⁴.

Interest in the versatile chemistry⁵ of acetylacetone prompted a study of its action as S.A.S. since it could behave as a depolarizer⁶, as well as a strong chelating ligand⁵.

Experimental

Materials : All chemicals used were of reagent grade. In the electrodeposition of nickel the bath consisted⁷ of NiSO₄·7H₂O (75 g/l), NaCl (15g/l) and H₃BO₃ (15 g/l), while that for zinc contained⁷ ZnSO₄·7H₂O (215 g/l), Al₂(SO₄)₃·18H₂O (30 g/l) and Na₂SO₄·10H₂O (50 g/l).

Efficiency measurements : The cathode current efficiency was estimated by measuring the total quantity of electricity passed using a copper coulometer.

The efficiency of the hydrogen evolution during the electrodeposition was separately determined using a hydrogen gas coulometer. This was carried out at the same experimental conditions at which the efficiency of the metal deposition was measured.

Polarization measurements : These measurements were carried out galvanostatically. The electrode potential was measured against a saturated calomel electrode.

Throwing power : The throwing power (A) of the studied baths was calculated⁸ from the weight ratio of the deposit on two cathodes of equal surface area (2 cm × 1 cm) but placed at different distances from the anode (15 and 40 cm). Thus,

$$A = \frac{W_1}{W_2} \cdot 100$$

where W₁ and W₂ refer to the weight of the deposit at the far and near cathode respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Throwing power cell.

The plating time of the unstirred bath was 45-60 minutes. A freshly prepared bath was used for each experiment. The nickel and zinc baths were maintained at pH 5.2 and 4.0 respectively.

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TABLE 1—THE CURRENT EFFICIENCY OF METAL DEPOSITION AND HYDROGEN EVOLUTION AT DIFFERENT CURRENT DENSITIES AND ACETYLACETONE CONCENTRATIONS AT 30°C

Ref. No.	Metal ion	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Acetylacetonone Concentration (mole/l)													
			—		0.001		0.005		0.010		0.050		0.075		0.10	
			M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %	M%	H ₂ %
1.	Zinc	5.0	94.4	5.0	96.0	2.5	97.0	2.0	96.0	2.0	92.1	1.5	90.5	2.0	87.0	4.0
2.		10.0	94.4	5.0	97.5	1.5	99.0	—	100.0	—	80.2	3.0	76.0	4.0	74.6	8.0
3.		15.0	94.6	5.0	97.8	1.5	100.0	—	100.0	—	91.1	3.0	80.5	5.0	78.5	9.0
4.		20.0	94.5	4.0	98.0	1.0	100.0	—	100.0	—	97.0	1.5	92.0	3.5	89.6	5.0
1.	Nickel	5.0	88.2	11.0	(a)	10.0	(a)	9.0	(a)	8.0	91.7	6.0	88.2	4.0	81.7	3.5
2.		10.0	81.6	18.0	(a)	12.0	(a)	9.0	(a)	6.0	97.9	2.0	97.4	1.5	96.7	2.5
3.		15.0	50.0	48.5	(a)	30.0	(a)	21.0	(a)	10.0	95.8	2.5	95.8	2.5	95.8	3.5
		20.0	24.6	74.0	(a)	52.0	(a)	30.0	(a)	13.0	96.4	2.5	98.8	1.0	97.2	2.0

(a) Spongy and poor quality deposit which is difficult to handle was obtained.

Results and Discussion

The dependence of the cathodic current efficiency, relating to metal deposition, on both the acetylacetonone concentration and the current density is shown in Table 1. The overall cathodic action during the deposition of zinc or nickel in the presence of acetylacetonone could comprise the following competing processes, (i) metal ion discharge, (ii) hydrogen evolution, and (iii) acetylacetonone reduction. The relative contribution of each of the three processes to the overall cathodic reaction is evident from the data of Table 1. For zinc deposition, there is a slight increase in current efficiency with increase of acetylacetonone concentration up to a certain level, beyond which a gradual decrease occurs. In the case of nickel solution, a considerable increase in efficiency is observed especially at high current densities. This observation is explained by the mixed effects (i-iii). Thus, acetylacetonone could be readily reduced on the deposited zinc electrode which is not the case for nickel⁶.

The zinc deposition is expected to take place from the hydrated metal ion and not from its acetylacetonate complex which could not be formed at this acidic condition⁵. However, nickel deposition can occur, under the experimental condition, from both the hydrated ion and the trimeric nickel acetylacetonate⁵ ([Ni(acac)₃]₃; Hacac=acetylacetonone). The latter is known to be formed at nearly neutral or slightly acidic conditions⁵.

In the case of zinc deposition in the presence of low concentration of acetylacetonone the main role of the ligand is the inhibition of the hydrogen evolution. This conclusion is supported by the decrease in current efficiency of hydrogen evolution at low concentrations of acetylacetonone and by increase in hydrogen evolution at higher concentrations (Table 1).

The situation with nickel is different from that of zinc. The former is expected to have a low hydrogen overpotential⁹ and consequently the carbonyl and carboxy compounds are difficult to be reduced on it. Accordingly, the inhibitor role of acetylacetonone is manifested at higher concentration. At low values of current densities, however, a slight contribution of acetylacetonone as a depolarizer could account for the observed decrease in the efficiency of nickel deposition at acetylacetonone concentrations higher than 0.05M.

The foregoing arguments could be substantiated by the polarization curves shown in Fig. 2. In the case of zinc, the presence of acetylacetonone produced an obvious depolarization effect especially at low current densities where the cathodic potentials are less negative than those of the hydrogen evolution. The inhibition effect of acetylacetonone became dominant at more negative potentials and higher

Fig. 2. Cathodic polarization curves for the deposition of nickel and zinc from solutions containing acetylacetonone.

current densities as the main cathodic process is only metal deposition. This behaviour is in accordance with the results of the current efficiency

measurements of Table 1. The corresponding measurements for nickel indicate that the effect of acetylacetonate on the cathodic polarization of nickel deposition appears to be mainly an inhibition one. The shift of the cathodic potentials towards higher values by the addition of acetylacetonate does not necessarily imply that the hydrogen evolution process becomes easier. This is in agreement with the observed increase in the deposition efficiency of nickel in the presence of acetylacetonate (Table 1).

It is worth mentioning in this connection that the cathodic deposition of zinc takes place in the region of its zero charge point whereas that of the nickel is shifted to the negative side¹⁰. This observation is explained by the adsorption of the nickel acetylacetonate (via the residual positive charge on the metal ion) which will consequently favour the nickel deposition process rather than the hydrogen evolution on the nickel cathode. In the presence of zinc ions, however the free acetylacetonate molecule could be adsorbed, which leads to its reduction; a process that leads to the observed decrease in the efficiency of the metal deposition.

The final distribution of a certain metal deposit is a function of factors like the polarizability and the variations in the current efficiency¹¹. The effect of the latter factor on the zinc deposition indicates that the throwing power increases at low concentration of acetylacetonate, while at a higher concentration of the ligand the phenomenon is reversed (Table 2). The polarizability is almost unchanged by the addition of acetylacetonate which leaves the current efficiency as the only operating factor. The throwing power of the studied nickel bath is decreased by the addition of acetylacetonate. The data of Table 1 indicate that the variation of the current efficiency with the current density should result into lower values for the throwing power (Table 2). In this case the polarizability increases by the addition of acetylacetonate (Fig. 2).

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF ACETYLACETONATE ON THE THROWING POWER OF ZINC AND NICKEL BATHS AT 20 mA cm⁻² AND 30°C

Ref. No.	Acetylacetonate concentration (mole/l)	Throwing power %	
		Zinc	Nickel
1.	—	9.0	31.2
2.	0.001	14.0	(a)
3.	0.005	15.0	(a)
4.	0.010	13.5	(a)
5.	0.050	10.4	27.0
6.	0.075	10.5	17.7
7.	0.100	10.8	13.2

(a) See footnote of Table 1 for significance.

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